

Portrayal Of Women Exploitation And Call For Social Change In The Fictions Of Arundhati Roy

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 28, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Torments, Decrees, Yelp, Emancipation, Conscience, Amelioration</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4837119</p>	<p><i>Arundhati Roy is a worldwide renowned writer activist. Roy dedicates her writing to promote the equality of all. She demonstrates exceptional consciousness of the social evils and understanding of the problems. She is concerned with contemporary socio-political matters and by highlighting the age-old torments of the helpless women, Roy condemns the deep-rooted social systems of exploitation. Her writings focus on the subjugation and maltreatment of Indian women folk, specifically customary decrees inflicted on women. This paper intends to unveil the subtle process of subjugation and gender differentiation in an orthodox, male-centred familial and societal setup where females have a relegated role and are dispossessed of elementary rights. The dream of Arundhati Roy is to change the world by raising a voice against the prevailing injustice, discrimination and convention of the society which effort to marginalise women into nothingness, overpower and control their identity in a boundary. The yelp for independence and emancipation by the women can be realised in the novels of Arundhati Roy. Being socially committed, Roy aims to scratch the readers' conscience and enflame them to contemplate on nation's social evils and discrimination so that it may lead to the amelioration of the society. The paper will enable the readers to perceive the intention of the fictionist in eliminating the social evil and change the status and image of the Indian woman. A qualitative research methodology has been employed to analyse and accumulate the germane data employing the textual analysis method. For this analytical research, the fictions written by Arundhati Roy viz, "The God of Small Things" (1997) and "The Ministry of Utmost Happiness" (2017) have been read and analysed.</i></p>

Introduction

India is traditionally observed as a male-dominated society. For ages, the womenfolk have been suppressed, exploited and confined within the four walls of the house with no identity of their own. Their needs and desires were not taken into consideration by the patriarchal society. Meena Usmani says in her article "Violence against Women": "The women have frequently been ruthlessly exploited in our society and the problem is growing day by day. The case of eve teasing, sexual harassment, abduction, sati, rape and wife battering at the public and at the workplace etc. have been more regularly reported since the 1960s, the issue of violence against women are discriminated at work, home and denied their due in every field. The constitution of India promises freedom, equality, opportunity and protection to women and give them several rights. In spite of that they enjoy an unequal status" (Usmani, P 42).

In Post- Independence India, women began to acknowledge their rights and became economically independent. Amongst these women, there was a struggle for the realisation of one's self. They started to redefine their roles in society. The emerging woman paves her path and marches ahead to catch up with the rest of the world. According to the patriarchal society, women recognise the actual status in the society- as a mother, wife and daughter. Ashok Kumar comments: "In modern times she is accepted as a professional, but when she protests against injustice and exploitation, she is grudgingly termed activist and seen as a rebel or as a deviant" (Kumar, P 21).

In modern India, even after so many years of Independence, women exploitation and gender discrimination in contemporary society are at their vilest. The causes and reasons that create challenges and sufferings for females in Indian society can be comprehended through the understandings and acquaintances of Arundhati Roy as she has exhibited in her fictions. Arundhati Roy's efforts can be observed in her fictions by the way she portrays the desires, needs and agonies of women as well as the hypocrisy and double standards of men. Both the fictions of Roy **depict the caste and gender subalternity from ahistorical perspective**. Patriarchal societies have always subjugated matriarchal societies and it is noticeable that patriarchal societies endorse the

male rather than the female and she remained outside of the hegemonic power structure. As Simon-De-Beauvoir avows,

“women lack concrete means for organizing themselves into a unit which can stand face to face with the correlative unit. They have no past, no history, no religion of their own, and they have no such solidarity of work and interest as that of the proletariat...they live dispersed among the males, attached through residence, housework, economic condition, and social standing to certain main- fathers or husbands- more firmly than they are to other women.” (Simon, p 19)

“*The God of Small Things*” depicts an accurate image of the miseries of Indian women as well as their submission and degradation in the patriarchal society. The fiction also represents their struggle to seek a sense of identity in a spiteful society. Women in these societies in the fiction are treated as chattels by their male counterparts. This fiction deals with the significant issues of gender disparity and feminism in a patriarchal setup where women have no voice to speak their issues. They are seldom permitted to be educated and men always have control over women. Ranga Rao in his scholarly paper pertinently observes: “Roy’s book is the only one I can think of among Indian novels in English which can be comprehensively described as a protest novel. It is all about atrocities against minorities, small things: children and youth, women and untouchables” (Rao, P13).

“*The God of Small Things*” deals with the adversities and hardships of females as a daughter and a spouse in a male-controlled society. Ammu was deprived of her parent’s love as her mother has no understanding and compassion for her daughter. She was not permitted to acquire higher education just because she is a female. Pappachi asserted that university education is: “an unnecessary expense for a girl”. Mammachi has experienced feebleness as a woman as she was being maltreated by her husband in the past. Despite this, she never hesitates to penalise Ammu & Velutha and her approach towards Velutha is akin to an animal. She is staggered and expresses her belligerence towards Ammu for loving an outcast,

“how could she stand the smell? They have a particular smell, these paravans,” (TGOST, 257)

Even Ammu experiences ill-treatment from her husband. Ammu thought that she has found her identity after marriage but in a short time, her dream shattered when her spouse compelled her to go to Mr. Hollick to protect his job. Even then, “he lunged at her, grabbed her hair, punched her and then passed out from the effort.” (TGOST, 42)

This society fails to accept man less woman and put up with fatherless children. A divorced daughter from a love marriage has no place in her parent’s home but contradictorily her brother, Chacko after his divorce was welcomed as inheritor of the family’s wealth. It was also shocking when Chacko flirted with women, he was supported by his mother Mammachi but for Ammu all this was against society and traditions so she was battered and closed in a room. Her brother, Chacko tried to marginalise her but her contravention of the caste, class and religion turned her into a rebellion and transgressor against this social boundary.

The actual catastrophe comes in Ammu’s life when she comes in the affinity with Velutha. Though there was an enormous caste distinction between Velutha and Ammu yet they participated in sex act because of their yearning and they did not pay any heed to the code of conduct and decrees of their respective castes. This sort of illegitimate affair was not tolerable and was measured as a societal crime to be castigated harshly. Even Mammachi alleged,

“Ammu had defiled the generations of breeding and brought the family to its knees. For generations to come, forever now, people would point at them at weddings and funerals. At baptism and birthday parties” (TGOST, 258).

The remaining part of Ammu’s life gets full of despondence tinged with fruitless daydreaming. She perishes in a soiled and grubby room of ‘Bharat Lodge’ in Alleppey. Amarnath Prasad gives a brief but powerful description of Ammu’s character by saying: “Through the character of Ammu, Arundhati Roy lashes out at the hypocritical moral code of society, which makes a difference between men and women”. (Prasad, 117).

Women are not only degraded and abused in India but are ill-treated in occidental cultures by white people also. Roy reveals this issue through an incident when an American intoxicated male bellowed at Rahel: “Black bitch! Suck my dick!” (TGOSM, 179). Arundhati Roy became prominent for her social activity and her involvement in many revolts to usher transformation in society. Roy is an author with a reason behind every endeavour; there is a determination to generate an improved position for the deprived. The present fiction is an account of exploitation, degradation, rejection, and brutalisation of subaltern people and marginalised. Through her narrative, Roy demarcates the humiliation and discrimination of untouchables as well as the wretched condition of religious minorities in a nation with Hindus in the majority, the oppression of womenfolk, the dispossession of tribals and transgenders from their constitutional rights. The strings of marginality pervade through the heart of the fiction *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*. The protagonists in the novel create themselves in their reactions to the present social circumstances. One of the protagonists Anjum is a hermaphrodite and a mother who is not born-Anjum rather she shapes herself. A significant part of the novel deals with Anjum’s journey of turning into her. Nazia Hasan scripts, “Anjum/Aftab becomes a metaphorical being, personifying many things simultaneously. Through her, Roy announces to deal with, stand with all those issues of society which may be gross, unwanted, unexpected, subaltern and pushed to the margins.” (Hasan, 111) The urge for identity echoes

from the very beginning of the novel. Anjum tussles with the society as well as its politics both in her orthodox Muslim family and at Khwabagh. She was compelled to abandon education because social arrangement enforced a limit on her, to move and think individualistically. When Aftab learns that his lovely, feminine singing voice is the cause of mocking from other children, he gets perplexed and retreats into a self-protective shell refusing to go to school or sing (and be further anguished by children who don't quite understand what he is.) "*He's a She. He's not a He or a She. He's a He and a She. She-He, He-She.*" (TMOUH, 16) Roy portrays the predicament of the transgenders in a nation like India where every person revel in democracy and has equal civil rights. Khwabagh gave refuge to a varied community of transgenders.

All the characters in the novel fight for their existence and try to restore their identity. Females are perceived as feeble and their identity can be sabotaged easily. The Naxalite and Maoist uprising was catalysed by turmoil and deprivation. The portrayal of Revathy's rape was unspeakable and dreadful: "There were six policemen around me. One was cutting my skin with a knife-blade ... They are smoking and putting their cigarettes on me ... you are a great heroine.... How many innocent girls have you sent to join your Party? You are spoiling everyone. Now you go and marry someone. Settle down quietly. But first, we will give you some marriage experience. They kept on burning me and cutting me... all raped me many times" (20)

In every stratum of society, womenfolk are considered the most peripheral. Arundhati Roy's fictions record the account of female's marginality and their mistreatment. The lady protagonist in Roy's debut novel "*The God of Small Things*" endured physical and mental distress perpetrated by the police officer as she valiantly loved an outcast person. In the fiction *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*, S. Tillotama also encountered similar pugnacity and embarrassment because of her audacious love for Musa, a Kashmiri Militant. Tilo was immodestly goaded by rigorous questionings, "How many men do you fuck at the same time?" (TMOUH, 422-23)

The doubly marginalised situation of whores is depicted by the narrator. They are not only disregarded and unheeded as females but also as 'sex workers'. This delimits them to avail the rights enjoyed by other privileged citizens. The condition of prostitutes is more miserable than other women. The novelist delineates the instance of Anwar Bhai, the brothel keeper of G B road whorehouse to accentuate their utmost feebleness and vulnerability. The whore Rubina expired due to a sudden burst of the appendix. The dead body of Rubina was discharged with the missing eyes and the authority of the hospital reported them with a fabricated justification, "rats had got to them in the mortuary" (TMOUH, 78) Nevertheless, the reality was poignant:

"Rubina's eyes had been stolen by someone who knew that a bunch of whores and their pimp were unlikely to complain to the police" (TMOUH, 78). They also "could not find a bathhouse to bathe Rubina's body, a graveyard to bury her in, or an imam to say prayers" (TMOUH, 78) Their rights are seized due to marginalisation process and these outcasts are not even able to voice or oppose exploitation.

Thus, with the voices of Anjum, Tilo, Revathy, Rubina and other castaways; Roy's fiction "*The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*" becomes a fiction of polyphonic protest to have a place for the self that is alienated and ostracised, "deliberately silenced, or preferably unheard."

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that Arundhati Roy has demonstrated gender distinction and exploitation in a very conspicuous and understandable way in both fictions. Roy's novels present the undesirable anguishes of womenfolk who have to endure the never-ending ordeal mutely and docilely. It is the noble and audacious attempt of the fictionist to evoke social mindfulness amongst the females.

The novels of Arundhati Roy criticise human society in general and Indian society in particular. Being an egalitarian, Roy invites widespread social transformation; application of impartiality before the law, fair chances of service, liberty from curbing rules and obsolete precepts. Roy appeals for women's emancipation and liberation of the entire society. Her objective is defined as a temporary stage within a larger conception of comprehensive liberation since the actual freedom of women or any other social section is unachievable in a tyrannical and spiteful social system. Through her female characters, Roy suggests that humiliation can be curbed only if the woman has economic independence and even if she divorces or is threatened with divorce, she can rely on herself and make both ends meet. A female ought to be self-assured and foster internal potency that will be conducive to resist the belligerence of a society that stresses her to abide by worn-out social standards. Females need to understand that while enduring suppression they are paying a price, so it is better to pay for individualism than for bondage. Roy advocates that Women must have the acquaintance that no rights will be realised without pressure. Womenfolk must organise to become a recognisable social force and try to alter the obsolete decrees. To lure attention and upsurge their social authority, females should collaborate with other exploited groups in society. Roy deems that the persecution of the Indian woman will not be alleviated without a radical transformation in the social setup.

REFERENCES:

Ahmad, Aijaz. (2006) Reading Arundhati Roy Politically, in Murari Prasad (ed.) Arundhati Roy: Critical Perspectives. Delhi: Pencraft International.

- Beauvoir, Simone de. (1949) *The Second Sex (Le deuxiemesexe)* Paris trans. and ed. H. M. Parshley, London:Jonahan Cape,19.
- Barche, G.D. (1999) “The God of Small Things: A study in Contradictions and Constraints”. Explorations Arundhati Roy’s *The God of Small Things*. New Delhi: Nice Printing Press.
- Hasan, N. (2017). Arundhati Roy and New Inscription on Autumn Leaves. International Conference on Language, Innovation, Culture, and Education, 8ICLICE-111.
- Kumar, Ashok. (2006) “Women Empowerment through Indo-Anglian Literature”, *Critical Responses to Feminism* ed. Binod Mishra. New Delhi: Sarup and Sons. 21.
- Kundu, Rama. (2007) *Indian Women Novelists in English* (ed.) Birendra Pandey, Delhi: Swaroop & Sons, 13.
- Mendes, A. C, & Lau. L. (2019). The precarious lives of India’s Others: The creativity of precarityin Arundhati Roy’s *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*, *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, 1744- 9863.
- Narasimhiah, C.D. (1986) “The Function of Criticism in India”, *Central Institute of Indian Languages*. Mysore.
- Prasad, Amarnath. (2006) “Feminism and Gender Discrimination in *The God of Small Things*.” *Critical Responses to Feminism*. New Delhi: Sarup and Sons.
- Roy, Arundhati. (2002) **The God of Small Things**. Gurgaon: Penguin Books India.
- Roy,A. (2017) *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*. Penguin Random House India pvt. Ltd, Gurgoan,29-30.
- Rao, Ranga. (1997) “Booker of the Year”. *The Hindu*. Sunday, Nov23, 13.
- Usmani, Meena. (2000) “Violence against Women”. *University News Magazine*, New Delhi, Vol 38, 42.

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